

Orthodontic Camouflage in a Patient with Mild Skeletal Class II Malocclusion

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ABSTRACT

Camouflage is the masking of underlying skeletal problem by treating only dental problems. This case report describes a 14 years 2 months old Asian male presented with increased overjet on mild Class-II skeletal base with average vertical facial proportions. Treatment involved orthodontic camouflage by extracting maxillary first premolars with correction of proclined incisors in the upper arch. Treatment took 18 months in completion in which patient profile and esthetics were significantly improved.

Keywords: camouflage, premolar extractions, fixed orthodontics

INTRODUCTION

According to Angle's system of classification, Class II is the most common type of malocclusion in which class II division 1 is 32% prevalent in Pakistan.¹ Treatment option for class II malocclusion is decided by its etiology.² Various options for its treatment include camouflage by extracting premolars using conventional orthodontics, growth modification using functional appliance combined with orthodontic treatment or orthognathic surgery combined with orthodontics.³ In some cases if the patient is not willing for extraction, distalization is the alternative option. Distalization can be done by extra oral traction or intraoral appliance for example catelin appliance or Wilson distalizing arch.⁴ Increased overjet also creates psychosocial problems. Quality of life may be affected and patient may feel social issues confronting others.⁵ Treatment of increased overjet reduces these psychosocial issues and self-esteem in patients increases. Furthermore, recent studies show that increased overjet increases the chance of injury to anterior teeth however the extent of trauma is minimal.⁶

This case report describes the treatment of a young male with increased overjet on mild skeletal class II base by extracting upper first premolars with absolute anchorage using temporary anchorage devices for the retraction of anterior teeth.

DIAGNOSIS

A 14 years 2 months old Asian male presented with the chief complaint of forwardly placed upper front teeth with no significant medical or dental history. On initial examination temporomandibular joint was also normal. The extra oral clinical examination showed (figure 1) convex profile with no gross deformity or asymmetry in

facial appearance. Nasolabial angle was obtuse. Intraoral examination showed Angle class II malocclusion with both molar and canine in class II bilaterally. Overjet was 9mm and overbite was 4mm (figure 2). Mild spacing in upper arch and mild crowding in lower arch was also observed (figure 3). Curve of spee was 2mm bilaterally.

The cephalometric analysis (table 1) revealed a mild skeletal class II anteroposterior relationship with an ANB of 6° and a Wits appraisal of 1mm. Skeletal pattern remained class II even after Eastman correction which converted it to 5.5°. The vertical proportions, assessed by the maxillary mandibular plane angle (23°), Sn-MP angle (33°) and face height ratio (56.8%) indicate a normal angle case with slightly increased anterior face height. Clinically, the upper incisors were slightly proclined and that was verified by the cephalometric findings of UI-SN (109°) and UI-PP (119°). The lower incisors were also slightly increased as IMPA was (96°). Upper and lower lips were both normal relative to Rickett's E plane with an obtuse nasolabial angle (116°).

TREATMENT OBJECTIVES

The following treatment objectives were determined:

1. Alignment of teeth and correction of overjet.
2. Correction of dental midlines and making them coincident with the facial midline.
3. Establish class I canine relationship bilaterally.
4. Finish with stable molar relationship, class I or class II, bilaterally.
5. Optimize dentofacial esthetics with orthodontic treatment and detailing of soft tissue profile.

TREATMENT ALTERNATIVES

We presented the following treatment options to the patient:

1. Growth medication with functional appliance
2. Extraction of upper first premolars
3. Orthognathic surgery once the growth is ceased.

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Patient opted the extraction plan as he was more prone towards least invasive and definitive treatment results, so

the extraction of upper first premolars was selected which reduced the overjet and corrected the inclinations of upper incisor as well.

Figure 1: Extraoral Photographs:

Figure 2: Pretreatment Photographs: Intraoral

TREATMENT PROGRESS

Upper and lower arches were banded and bonded with pre-adjusted edgewise fixed appliances (0.022” x 0.028” slot) with MBT prescription and 0.016”nickle titanium (Niti) was ligated. Initial leveling and alignment took 6 months. After extraction of first premolars temporary anchorage devices were screwed between upper second premolars and first molars and retraction of anterior were started with power chain using 175gm force were given (Figure 3). Retraction of upper incisors was completed using asymmetrical forces and kobayashi hook was tied on upper left lateral incisor and class 1 elastics given to correct midline. Midlines were corrected with molars in full cusp class II and canines in class I bilaterally. It took 8 months to retract the anteriors and to correct the overjet. Settling was done by settling elastics (Figure 4). Triangular elastics 3/8 were given to settle premolar by 50 gm force. Follow-up appointments were given for the settling of teeth and the correction of curve of spee. Debanding and debonding was done after 18 months of

treatment. Vacuum formed retainers were given.

TREATMENT RESULTS

After 18 months of active treatment overjet was corrected with the establishment of full unit class II molar relationship and the class I canine relationship bilaterally (Figure 6). Overbite was reduced to 30% with the dental midlines became coincident with each other and with the facial midline at the end of treatment. Mutually protected occlusion was established having canine guidance on left and right lateral excursions with no working or non-working side interferences. Anterior guidance on protrusion was established on posterior disocclusion. Radiographic evaluation showed increased interincisal angle (Table 1), it was mainly contributed by the retraction of upper anteriors. The decrease in nasolabial angle can be explained due to growth changes as evident from superimposition (figure 7). The value of SNA and SNB remained same because only vertical growth was noticed.

On Cephalometric superimposition it was noticed that maxillary anterior retraction was done successfully with controlled tipping (Figure 7). No root resorption on

incisors were seen and patient was satisfied with his profile. During retention period occlusal relationship was maintained with the preservation of periodontium.

Figure 3: Mid Treatment Photographs: Anterior retraction after leveling and alignment

Figure 4: Settling of teeth using triangular settling elastics 3/8, 50gm force

Table 1: Cephalometric Measurement:

Variable	Pre-Treatment	Post Treatment	Change
SNA	82o	82o	0°
SNB	76o	76o	0°
ANB	6o	6o	0°
SN to mandible plane	33o	34o	+1°
SN to maxillary plane	10o	13o	3°
Wits appraisal	+1mm	+1.5mm	+0.5mm
Upper incisor to maxillary plane angle	119o	108o	11°
Lower incisor to mandibular plane angle	96o	93o	-3°
Interincisal angle	122o	136o	+14°
MM angle	22o	21o	+1°
Upper anterior face height	43 mm	49 mm	7 mm
Lower anterior face height	55 mm	60 mm	5 mm
Face height ratio	52 %	51.3 %	-0.7 %
Lower incisor to Apo Line	2 mm	0.5 mm	-1.5 mm
E-Centroid	3 mm	2 mm	-1 mm
Upper lip to Ricketts E Plane	-1 mm	-2 mm	-1 mm
Lower lip to Ricketts E Plane	0mm	0mm	0 mm
Nasolabial Angle	116o	114o	-2°

Figure 5: End Of Active Treatment Extraoral Photographs:

Figure 6: End Of Active Treatment Intraoral Photographs

Maxillary Superimposition

Mandibular Superimposition

DISCUSSION

Malocclusion can be treated in several ways depending upon the characteristics like anteroposterior discrepancy, age and patient preference. One of the major reasons patients seek orthodontic treatment is to improve their esthetics. In the orthodontic literature, the perception of ideal facial esthetics, mainly identified with the patient's profile, and the employment of either one of the two main treatment approaches ,extraction or non-extraction, have been highly controversial issues. It has been explained in the study of Sneha Lata Verma and VP Sharma that the extraction or non-extraction decision, if based on sound diagnostic criteria, seems to have no systematic detrimental effects on the facial profile.⁷ It also has been argued that extraction treatment, and backward pulling mechanics cause the detrimental effect on the temporomandibular joint but in the mentioned case after the extraction of premolars and retracting anteriors, TMJ remained normal. Patient followed for 2

years for the evaluation of facial profile. Further the profile was improved after incisor retraction and there was no dish-in appearance of the facial profile as it was also evident from the study that profile either get improved throughout treatment or at least remained satisfactory in class II division 1 cases. Other than extraction and non extraction treatment, orthognathic surgery is another option for treating class II malocclusion but it's an invasive procedure.

Growth modification can also be considered in this case. From the superimposition it is evident that considerable growth occurred in the vertical direction in this patient, but skeletal relationship remained same because anteroposterior growth occurred in equal proportion. Hence the decision of not going for growth modification and getting extraction treatment was in favor of patient's preference of seeking least invasive and definite

treatment outcome. Settling of teeth was done in the ramal growth and overbite was corrected by posterior extrusions in the space gained by this vertical growth because it is evident in studies that posterior extrusions are stable.

CONCLUSION

Class II camouflage is challenging until proper diagnosis and treatment plan with appropriate mechanics are done. Reduction in overjet, improvement in facial esthetics, and functional occlusion was achieved after the planned extraction of upper first premolars in this case.

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